

EFFECT OF THE NUMBER OF LAMINATIONS ON BENDING AND TRANSVERSE SHEAR PROPERTIES OF PLAIN WEAVE FABRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, bending and transverse shear properties of plain weave fabric composite laminates are investigated considering the intra-lamina inhomogeneity through finite element analysis. Using the homogenization procedures, both effective 3D continuum properties and effective Reissner-Mindlin plate properties are calculated. Then, the effect of the number of laminations on the laminate bending stiffness and the transverse shear stiffness, in other words, the effect of the intra-lamina inhomogeneity on the laminate stiffness, is investigated. Through the numerical investigation, it is found that if the number of plies of laminate is small, bending stiffness and transverse shear stiffness of the laminate are significantly decrease compared to those evaluated on the assumption that each lamina has homogeneous effective 3D continuum properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials reinforced with weave fabric are increasingly applied to the structural members in the aerospace and automotive engineering fields. These weave fabric composites are often used in the forms of laminated plates or shells. When evaluating the mechanical properties of these composite laminates, each lamina is usually treated as the homogeneous material. However, due to the architecture of weave fabric, the intra-lamina inhomogeneity of constituent materials' mechanical properties is more influential in the weave fabric composite than in the uni-directionally fiber reinforced composite. In the weave fabric composite laminate with small number of plies, which could be locally formed in the laminate with delamination cracks, this intra-lamina inhomogeneity may affect the mechanical properties, especially bending and transverse shear properties those are closely related to the buckling properties, of composite laminate. This issue is very important to design light weight structures with using thin thickness composite laminates.

In this study, bending and transverse shear properties of plain weave fabric composite laminates, especially the laminates with small number of laminations, are investigated considering the intra-lamina inhomogeneity through finite element (FE) analysis. To simplify the FE modelling, it is assumed that all laminae (all plies) included in the laminate have the same fiber direction and that the weave structures of all laminae are aligned along thickness direction (there is no gap of weave structure in in-plane direction between plies). First, assuming the number of laminations is infinite, therefore assuming the out-of-plane as well as the in-plane periodic properties of fabric composite, the effective 3D continuum properties of the composite (elastic properties as a bulk material) are calculated using homogenization procedures [1-4]. Next, taking into consideration the in-plane periodic properties of fabric composite laminate and using the homogenization procedures, the effective Reissner-Mindlin plate bending and transverse shear properties of the composite laminate are calculated [5-11]. Then, the effect of the number of laminations on the laminate bending stiffness and the transverse shear stiffness, in other words, the effect of the intra-lamina inhomogeneity on the laminate stiffness, is investigated.

In this paper we use the convention that Latin indices i, j, k, l take the values 1, 2, 3 and Greek indices $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ take the values 1, 2 unless otherwise specified.

2 EFFECTIVE 3-D CONTINUUM ELASTIC PROPERTIES

In this section, assuming the number of laminations of plain weave fabric composite to be infinite, homogenization procedures to calculate the effective elastic properties of the fabric composite as the 3-D continuum body are described [1-4]. In this case, the fabric composite laminate (more precisely the composite body) has the out-of-plane periodicity (periodicity along thickness direction) as well as the in-plane periodicity. Thus, the 1-ply region is selected as a unit cell and the FE analysis model as shown in Fig.1 is prepared. Then the periodic boundary conditions as described below are applied to the unit cell analysis model.

Figure 1: Unit cell for equivalent 3-D continuum analysis.

The displacement at the point on the boundary surface of unit cell which has the outward normal vector to positive x_1 direction (or to negative x_1 direction) is expressed as $u_i^{+x_1}$ (or $u_i^{-x_1}$). In the same manner, the displacements on the other boundary surfaces are expressed as $u_i^{+x_2}$, $u_i^{-x_2}$, $u_i^{+x_3}$, or $u_i^{-x_3}$. Then, the periodic boundary conditions:

$$u_i^{+x_1} - u_i^{-x_1} = E_{i1}(2a) \quad (1)$$

$$u_i^{+x_2} - u_i^{-x_2} = E_{i2}(2a) \quad (2)$$

$$u_i^{+x_3} - u_i^{-x_3} = E_{i3}(h) \quad (3)$$

are applied to the unit cell FE model. In equation (1)-(3), E_{ij} is the macroscopic strain which means the averaged strain in the unit cell and a , h are the dimensions of unit cell shown in Fig.1.

After applying appropriate macroscopic strain E_{ij} to the unit cell through equation (1)-(3) and conducting the FE analysis, microscopic stress σ_{ij} within the unit cell is obtained. Then, macroscopic stress Σ_{ij} which means the averaged stress in the unit cell is calculated using the equation as follows:

$$\Sigma_{ij} = \frac{1}{|V|} \iiint_V \sigma_{ij} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \quad (4)$$

where V is the volume region of the unit cell and $|V|$ is its volume. Through these procedures, the relation between macroscopic stress Σ_{ij} and macroscopic strain E_{ij} can be obtained as follows:

$$\Sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} E_{kl} \quad (5)$$

where C_{ijkl} is the effective 3-D continuum stiffness tensor, which means the stiffness tensor of the 3-D continuum body that is equivalent to the fabric composite. The converse relation of equation (5) becomes

$$E_{ij} = S_{ijkl} \Sigma_{kl} \quad (S_{ijkl} \equiv C_{ijkl}^{-1}) \quad (6)$$

and the effective 3-D continuum compliance tensor S_{ijkl} can be obtained.

3 EFFECTIVE PLATE STIFFNESS

3.1 Effective Kirchhoff plate stiffness (effective plate bending stiffness)

In this subsection, homogenization procedures to calculate the effective plate stiffness of the fabric composite are described [5-10]. As the special procedures are necessary to calculate the effective plate transverse shear stiffness, those are described in section 3.2.

Because the top and bottom surfaces of the actual fabric composite laminate are traction free surfaces, the out-of-plane periodicity (periodicity in thickness direction) cannot be assumed. On the other hand, the in-plane periodicity can still be assumed. Thus the region that contains all of the plies is selected as a unit cell and the FE model as shown in Fig.2 is prepared.

Figure 2: Unit cell for equivalent plate analysis (4-ply laminate).

Then the in-plane periodic boundary conditions:

$$u_{\alpha}^{+x_1} - u_{\alpha}^{-x_1} = E_{\alpha 1}(2a) + K_{\alpha 1} x_3(2a) \quad , \quad u_3^{+x_1} - u_3^{-x_1} = -K_{12} x_2(2a) \quad (7), (8)$$

$$u_{\alpha}^{+x_2} - u_{\alpha}^{-x_2} = E_{\alpha 2}(2a) + K_{\alpha 2} x_3(2a) \quad , \quad u_3^{+x_2} - u_3^{-x_2} = -K_{12} x_1(2a) \quad (9), (10)$$

are applied to the unit cell FE model. In equation (7)-(10), $E_{\alpha\beta}$ is the macroscopic in-plane strain and $K_{\alpha\beta}$ is the macroscopic curvature and a is the dimension of unit cell shown in Fig.2.

After applying appropriate macroscopic strain $E_{\alpha\beta}$ and curvature $K_{\alpha\beta}$ to the unit cell through equation (7)-(10) and conducting the FE analysis, microscopic stress σ_{ij} within the unit cell is obtained. Then, macroscopic resultant force $N_{\alpha\beta}$ and macroscopic resultant moment $M_{\alpha\beta}$ are calculated using equations as follow:

$$N_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{|S|} \iiint_V \sigma_{\alpha\beta} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \quad , \quad M_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{|S|} \iiint_V x_3 \sigma_{\alpha\beta} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \quad (11), (12)$$

where V is the volume region of unit cell, S is the cross-section surface of unit cell at $x_3 = 0$ and $|S|$ is its area. Through these procedures, the relation between macroscopic resultant force and moment $N_{\alpha\beta}$, $M_{\alpha\beta}$ and macroscopic in-plane strain and curvature $E_{\alpha\beta}$, $K_{\alpha\beta}$ can be obtained as follow:

$$N_{\alpha\beta} = A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} E_{\gamma\delta} + B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} K_{\gamma\delta} \quad (13)$$

$$M_{\alpha\beta} = B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^T E_{\gamma\delta} + D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} K_{\gamma\delta} \quad (14)$$

where $A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$, $B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ and $D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ are the effective plate stiffness tensors, which means the stiffness tensor of plate that is equivalent to the fabric composite. The converse relations of equation (13), (14) become

$$E_{\alpha\beta} = A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^* N_{\gamma\delta} + B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^* M_{\gamma\delta} \quad (15)$$

$$K_{\alpha\beta} = B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{*T} N_{\gamma\delta} + D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^* M_{\gamma\delta} \quad (16)$$

and the effective plate compliance tensors $A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^*$, $B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^*$ and $D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^*$ can be obtained. To obtain the microscopic stress σ_{ij} in the case the macroscopic resultant force and moment $N_{\alpha\beta}$, $M_{\alpha\beta}$ are known, first macroscopic in-plane strain and curvature $E_{\alpha\beta}$, $K_{\alpha\beta}$ are calculated using equations (15), (16), and then those are used in equations (7)-(10).

3.2 Effective plate transverse shear stiffness

In the Reissner-Mindlin plate under cylindrical bending, the transverse shear stiffness F_{55} relates the resultant transverse shear force Q_{13} and the plate transverse shear strain γ_{13} as $Q_{13} = F_{55} \gamma_{13}$. In this subsection, homogenization procedures to calculate the effective plate transverse shear stiffness F_{55} of the fabric composite are described [11].

If the plate is under cylindrical bending, the resultant transverse shear force Q_{13} and the resultant bending moment M_{11} are related as:

$$Q_{13} = \frac{dM_{11}}{dx_1} \quad (17)$$

Let the microscopic stresses in the unit cell due to macroscopic transverse shear force Q_{13} and macroscopic bending moment M_{11} be expressed as $\sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}}$ and $\sigma_{ij}^{M_{11}}$ respectively. Then the microscopic stress due to both Q_{13} and M_{11} can be expressed as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}} + \sigma_{ij}^{M_{11}} = \sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}} + p_{ij}^{M_{11}=1} M_{11} \quad (18)$$

where $p_{ij}^{M_{11}=1}$ is the microscopic stress due to unit bending moment $M_{11}=1$ under cylindrical bending, which can be obtained through the procedures described in section 3.1. From manipulations of equation (18) using equation (17) as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}}}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial p_{ij}^{M_{11}=1}}{\partial x_j} M_{11} + p_{ij}^{M_{11}=1} \frac{\partial M_{11}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}}}{\partial x_j} + p_{i1}^{M_{11}=1} \frac{dM_{11}}{dx_1} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}}}{\partial x_j} + p_{i1}^{M_{11}=1} Q_{13} \quad (19)$$

and equilibrium equations $\partial \sigma_{ij} / \partial x_j = 0$,

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}}}{\partial x_j} + p_{i1}^{M_{11}=1} Q_{13} = 0 \quad (20)$$

can be derived, which is satisfied within the unit cell. Equation (20) means the equilibrium equation about $\sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}}$ when the body force $f_i = p_{i1}^{M_{11}} Q_{13}$ is applied. Thus, solving the equation (20) through FE analysis with periodic boundary conditions of equations (7)-(10) where $E_{\alpha\beta}$ and $K_{\alpha\beta}$ are set to be zero, $\sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}}$ can be obtained.

The equivalence of the complimentary strain energy within the unit cell due to $\sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}}$ and the complimentary strain energy in the homogenized plate due to Q_{13} is expressed as:

$$U_C^{Q_{13}} \equiv \iiint_V \frac{1}{2} s_{ijkl} \sigma_{ij}^{Q_{13}} \sigma_{kl}^{Q_{13}} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(Q_{13})^2}{F_{55}} \times |S| \quad (21)$$

where s_{ijkl} is the compliance tensor of the constituent material in the unit cell. The effective Reissner–Mindlin plate transverse shear stiffness F_{55} is evaluated using equation (21) as follows:

$$F_{55} = \frac{|S| (Q_{13})^2}{2 U_C^{Q_{13}}} \quad (22)$$

4 Results

4.1 Material system

In this study, bending and transverse shear properties of plain weave fabric CK6261C (Toray Industries, Inc.) reinforced epoxy resin #2500 composite laminates were investigated. Both warp and fill yarns (fiber bundles or tows) in plain weave fabric CK6261C consist of carbon fiber T700-12K. Geometric dimensions of this material system, which are shown in Fig.3, are summarized in Table 1. When generating the FE model, the shape of the yarn cross section was assumed to be ellipse with major axis length of w and minor axis length of t . Material properties of yarns were assumed to be equivalent to those of uni-directionally fiber reinforced composite with fiber volume fraction $V_f = 68.5\%$ and those are summarized in Table 2 [12]. Material properties of pure epoxy resin, which exists around the woven yarns in the composite laminate, is also shown in Table 2.

In the FE modelling (geometric modelling and mesh generation) of the fabric composite, the software TexGen [13] which was developed at the University of Nottingham, was utilised. Some in-house tools were developed to conduct the homogenization pre- or post-process and FE analysis was conducted using MSC. Marc 2013.

Figure 3: Geometric dimensions of plain weave fabric composite lamina.

Table 1: Geometric properties of fabric composite (unit: mm).

Yarn spacing (a)	Yarn width (w)	Fabric thickness ($2t$)	Ply thickness (h)
3.33	2.83	0.556	0.612

Table 2: Material properties of yarn and resin in fabric composite [12].

Yarn ($V_f = 68.5\%$)					Resin	
E_L	E_T	G_{LT}	G_{TT}	ν_{LT}	E	ν
GPa	GPa	GPa	GPa	–	GPa	–
157	4.14	1.90	1.49	0.30	3.45	0.35

4.2 3-D continuum elastic properties

When the macroscopic strain tensor E_{ij} and the macroscopic stress tensor Σ_{ij} are expressed in the vector forms as $\{\mathbf{E}\} = [E_{11} \ E_{22} \ E_{33} \ 2E_{23} \ 2E_{31} \ 2E_{12}]^T$ and $\{\mathbf{\Sigma}\} = [\Sigma_{11} \ \Sigma_{22} \ \Sigma_{33} \ \Sigma_{23} \ \Sigma_{31} \ \Sigma_{12}]^T$, the macroscopic strain-stress relation in equation (6) can be expressed in the matrix-vector form as:

$$\{\mathbf{E}\} = [\mathbf{S}]\{\mathbf{\Sigma}\} \quad (23)$$

The compliance matrix $[\mathbf{S}]$ in equation (23) specifies the effective 3-D continuum elastic properties. Numerical calculations for the plain weave fabric composite described in section 4.1 were conducted. Then the effective 3-D continuum compliance matrix $[\mathbf{S}]$ has the form of the orthotropic material as:

$$[\mathbf{S}] = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & -\nu_{13}/E_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & 1/E_2 & -\nu_{23}/E_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 1/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ & sym. & & & 1/G_{31} & 0 \\ & & & & & 1/G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

and results of the effective 3-D continuum elastic properties are summarized in Table 3 using the elastic constants shown in equation (24).

Table 3: Effective 3-D continuum properties of fabric composite.

$E_1 = E_2$	E_3	$G_{13} = G_{23}$	G_{12}	$\nu_{13} = \nu_{23}$	ν_{12}
GPa	GPa	GPa	GPa	–	–
41.1	4.87	1.52	1.62	0.457	0.142

4.3 Bending stiffness

When the macroscopic in-plane strain tensor $E_{\alpha\beta}$ and the macroscopic curvature tensor $K_{\alpha\beta}$ are expressed in the vector forms as $\{\mathbf{E}\} = [E_{11} \ E_{22} \ 2E_{12}]^T$ and $\{\mathbf{K}\} = [K_{11} \ K_{22} \ 2K_{12}]^T$, and the macroscopic resultant force tensor $N_{\alpha\beta}$ and the macroscopic moment tensor $M_{\alpha\beta}$ are expressed in the vector forms as $\{\mathbf{N}\} = [N_{11} \ N_{22} \ N_{12}]^T$ and $\{\mathbf{M}\} = [M_{11} \ M_{22} \ M_{12}]^T$, equation (15), (16) can be expressed in the matrix-vector form as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \mathbf{K} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{A}^*] & [\mathbf{B}^*] \\ [\mathbf{B}^*]^T & [\mathbf{D}^*] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

The compliance matrices $[\mathbf{A}^*]$, $[\mathbf{B}^*]$ and $[\mathbf{D}^*]$ in equation (25) specify the effective plate (effective

Kirchhoff plate) elastic properties. For the composite laminate described in section 4.1, the plate compliance matrices $[\mathbf{A}^*]$, $[\mathbf{B}^*]$ and $[\mathbf{D}^*]$ have the form as follow independent of the number of laminations:

$$[\mathbf{A}^*] = \begin{bmatrix} 1/\hat{A}_{11} & 1/\hat{A}_{12} & 0 \\ 1/\hat{A}_{12} & 1/\hat{A}_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\hat{A}_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \quad [\mathbf{B}^*] = [\mathbf{0}], \quad [\mathbf{D}^*] = \begin{bmatrix} 1/\hat{D}_{11} & 1/\hat{D}_{12} & 0 \\ 1/\hat{D}_{12} & 1/\hat{D}_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\hat{D}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (26), (27), (28)$$

\hat{D}_{11} in equation (28) is the effective plate bending stiffness ($M_{11} = \hat{D}_{11} K_{11}$) in the case of pure bending in x_1 direction ($M_{11} \neq 0$, $N_{\alpha\beta} = M_{22} = M_{12} = Q_{\alpha 3} = 0$).

When the composite laminates with various numbers of laminations (various numbers of plies) are assumed to be the homogeneous plates with the same thickness as the corresponding composite laminates and the material that constitutes those homogeneous plates was assumed to have the effective 3-D continuum elastic properties shown in Table 3, the bending stiffness \hat{D}_{11} of those homogeneous plates can be evaluated using Young's modulus E_1 as

$$\hat{D}_{11} = E_1 \frac{H^3}{12} \equiv \hat{D}_{11}^{3D} \quad (29)$$

where H is the homogeneous plate thickness. (In the case that the thickness of each ply is h and the number of laminations is n , $n \times h$ is used in H ($H = nh$)).

Numerical calculations were conducted following the procedures in section 3.1, and results of the effective plate bending stiffness are shown in Fig.4. In Fig.4, the effective plate bending stiffness \hat{D}_{11} is divided by \hat{D}_{11}^{3D} which is defined in equation (29) and these normalized bending stiffness $\hat{D}_{11} / \hat{D}_{11}^{3D}$ are plotted against the number of laminations. Fig.4 shows that if the number of laminations is small, the effective plate bending stiffness \hat{D}_{11} decreases compared to the homogeneous plate bending stiffness \hat{D}_{11}^{3D} . \hat{D}_{11} decreases by 72% compared to \hat{D}_{11}^{3D} in the case of 1-ply laminate and decreases by 8% in the case of 2-ply laminate. Therefore, if the bending stiffness of the composite laminate is evaluated based on the assumption that each ply is homogeneous material and the material has the effective 3-D continuum elastic properties especially the effective Young's modulus E_1 , which can be easily evaluated through tensile test and can be often found in the material specification data, then the bending stiffness of the composite would be overestimated. While, if the number of laminations is large (more than 12 or 14 in Fig.4), the bending stiffness of the laminate can be evaluated using equation (29).

Figure 4: Normalized bending stiffness variation with the number of laminations.

Fig.5 shows the bending stress distribution along laminate thickness direction in the case of pure bending in x_1 direction ($M_{11} = \bar{M}_{11}$, $N_{\alpha\beta} = M_{22} = M_{12} = Q_{\alpha 3} = 0$). Bending stress σ_{11} was calculated along the thickness direction at the center of yarn crossover region (see Fig.6). In Fig.5, results are plotted with dimensionless coordinate along thickness direction x_3/h (h : ply thickness) on the ordinate and a dimensionless bending stress $\sigma_{11}/(6\bar{M}_{11}/H^2)$ on the abscissa. In the case of the homogeneous plate under pure bending load $M_{11} = \bar{M}_{11}$, the bending stress can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{11} = \frac{\bar{M}_{11}}{(H^3/12)} x_3 = \frac{6\bar{M}_{11}}{H^2} \frac{x_3}{(H/2)} \quad (30)$$

The bending stress shown in equation (30) is also plotted in Fig.5 as “homogeneous plate”. Fig.5 shows that the bending stress fluctuates within the lamina due to the intra-lamina inhomogeneity and that if the number of laminations is small, the stress distribution significantly deviates from that of equation (30). While, if the number of laminations is large, e.g. in the case of 14-ply laminate, the fluctuation within the lamina remains but the distribution of the average stress in each lamina gets close to that of equation (30).

Figure 5: Bending stress distributions along laminate thickness direction
 (—○—: finite element analysis, ---- : homogeneous plate).

Figure 6: Stress evaluation points along laminate thickness direction.

4.4 Transverse shear stiffness

When the composite laminates with various numbers of laminations are assumed to be the homogeneous plates with the same thickness as the corresponding composite laminates and the material that constitute those homogeneous plates was assumed to have the effective 3-D continuum elastic properties shown in Table 3, the transverse shear stiffness F_{55} of those homogeneous plates can be evaluated using the shear modulus G_{13} and the shear correction factor $k = 5/6$ [14] as:

$$F_{55} = k G_{13} H = \frac{5}{6} G_{13} H \equiv F_{55}^{3D} \quad (31)$$

where H is the homogeneous plate thickness ($H = n \times h$). Numerical calculations were conducted following the procedures in section 3.2, and results of the effective plate transverse shear stiffness are shown in Fig.7. In Fig.7, the effective plate transverse shear stiffness F_{55} is divided by F_{55}^{3D} which is defined in equation (31) and the normalized transverse shear stiffness F_{55} / F_{55}^{3D} are plotted against the number of laminations. Fig.7 shows that if the number of laminations is small, the effective plate transverse shear stiffness F_{55} decreases compared to the homogeneous plate stiffness F_{55}^{3D} . F_{55} decreases by 26% compared to F_{55}^{3D} in case of 1-ply laminate, by 35% in the case of 2-ply laminate and by 13% in the case of 4-ply laminate. Therefore, if the transverse shear stiffness of the composite laminate is evaluated based on the assumption that each ply is homogeneous material and the material has the effective 3-D continuum elastic properties especially the effective shear modulus G_{13} (which cannot easily be evaluated through experiment in contrast to the Young's modulus E_1), then the transverse shear stiffness of the composite laminate would be overestimated. While, if the number of laminations is large, the transverse shear stiffness of the laminate can be evaluated using equation (31).

Fig.8 shows the transverse shear stress distribution along laminate thickness direction under the transverse shear load $Q_{13} = \bar{Q}_{13}$. Stress evaluation points are the same as those used in bending stress evaluation (see Fig.6). In Fig.8, results are plotted with dimensionless coordinate along thickness direction x_3/h (h : ply thickness) on the ordinate and a dimensionless transverse shear stress $\tau_{13}/(\bar{Q}_{13}/H)$ on the abscissa. In the case of the homogeneous plate under transverse shear load $Q_{13} = \bar{Q}_{13}$, the shear stress can be expressed as:

$$\tau_{13} = \frac{\bar{Q}_{13}}{H} \times \frac{3}{2} \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{x_3}{H/2} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (32)$$

The shear stress shown in equation (32) is also plotted in Fig.8 as “homogeneous plate”. Fig.8 shows

that the shear stress fluctuates within the lamina and that if the number of laminations is small, the stress distribution significantly deviates from that of equation (32). While, if the number of laminations is large, the fluctuation within the lamina remains but the distribution of the average stress in each lamina gets close to that of equation (32).

Figure 7: Normalized transverse shear stiffness variation with the number of laminations.

Figure 8: Transverse shear stress distributions along laminate thickness direction (—◇: finite element analysis, ----: homogeneous plate).

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, bending and transverse shear properties of plain weave fabric composite laminates, especially the laminates with small number of laminations, are investigated considering the intra-lamina inhomogeneity through finite element analysis. To simplify the finite element modelling, it is assumed that all laminae (all plies) included in the laminate have the same fiber direction and that the

weave structures of all laminae are aligned along thickness direction (there is no nesting in the laminate). Through the numerical investigation, it is found that if the number of laminations is small, bending stiffness and transverse shear stiffness of the laminate are significantly decrease compared to those evaluated on the assumption that each lamina is homogeneous with the effective 3-D continuum material properties.

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